

Cross Array Task (CAT) experimental protocol

Session ID:

Date:

Administrator:

School ID/name:

Class/Grade:

Pupil ID:

Pupil age:

Pupil sex:

Type of interaction:

- V: using voice commands;
- VS: using voice commands and hand gestures on an empty cross array;
- VSF: voice commands and hand gestures on an empty cross array, hinging on visual feedback;

Algorithm dimension:

- 2D: polychromatic colouring of patterns of dots, repetitions of patterns and symmetries;
- 1D: monochromatic colouring of patterns of dots
- 0D: colouring of individual dots

S1	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
Observations and notes			

S2	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
Observations and notes			

S3	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
Observations and notes			

S4	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
Observations and notes			

S5	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
Observations and notes			

S6	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
Observations and notes			

S7 	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
	Observations and notes		

S8 	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
	Observations and notes		

S9 	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
	Observations and notes		

S10 	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
	Observations and notes		

S11 	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
	Observations and notes		

S12 	Type of interaction (artefact and autonomy)		
	V	VS	VSF
	Algorithm dimension		
	2D	1D	0D
	Observations and notes		

Supplementary observations: